

EVALUATING PERFORMANCE OF CHICKPEA GENOTYPES FOR RESISTING TO *Helicoverpa armigera* (HUB.) THROUGHOUT THE GROWING SEASON AND CORRELATING WITH YIELD PARAMETER

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was worked out at the experimental Research Farm of the Department of Agricultural Entomology, VNMKV, Parbhani during *rabi*, 2021 expecting resistive outcomes from responses of chickpea genotypes against gram pod borer (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hub.) for eggs and larval population including pod damage per cent from vegetative to maturity stage during growing meteorological weeks (MW). The correlation of the screening parameter with yield has also been calculated. The mean eggs, larval infestation and pod damage per cent of gram pod borer, *H. armigera* on genotypes under study is presented in the present investigation. It is found that on genotypes indicated significant differences regarding eggs, larval population and pod damage of *H. armigera*. The mean number of eggs was reported on genotypes ICCL 86111 (0.24 eggs/plant). The least larval population was reported on genotypes ICCL 86111 (0.51 larvae/plant). The genotype ICCL 86111 had the least pod damage, 3.36 per cent and ICC 506 was (3.93 per cent) also fairly compatible genotype in this regard. followed by BDNG 797 (4.26 per cent), ICC 92944 (5.46 per cent), ICCV 10 (5.88 per cent) and JG 62 (7.15 per cent) respectively. The chickpea yield showed significant correlation in negative manner with mean pod damage per cent ($r = -0.774$). Significantly Negative correlation was found with morning relative humidity with pest incidence in the genotypes *viz.*, BDNG 797 and ICCL 86111.

KEYWORDS: Screening, *Helicoverpa armigera*, Eco-friendly, Host plant resistance, Pod damage, yield correlation, chickpea;

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INTRODUCTION:

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.), being primary pulse crop of the Fabaceae family and often known as "Bengal gram" and locally as "chana." As a superior and less expensive source of protein than meat, chickpeas are locally referred to as "poor man's meat". Through biological nitrogen fixation of up to 140 kg of atmospheric nitrogen ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ ultimately preserves soil fertility. During the 2020–2021 growing season in Maharashtra, chickpeas were grown over an area of 16.94 lac/ha, yielding 13.97 lakh tonnes and 824 kg/ha of productivity. Production and productivity in the Marathwada region are 10.59 lakh/ha, 7.76 lakh tonnes and 707 kg/ha, respectively [1]. One of the most significant obstacles to the production of chickpeas worldwide is the chickpea pod borer (*H. armigera*). It infects more than 182 different crop types and is a serious pest. There is a large population of *H. armigera* throughout Asia,

Africa, Australia, and Southern Europe [21]. *Helicoverpa armigera* affects chickpea from the early vegetative until podding stage, causing 60–80% of crop losses in Maharashtra state (India) [17]. The current research work was designed based on current hypotheses of *H. armigera* issue and the finding of pod borer (*H. armigera*) contesting genotypes of chickpea. Germplasm accessions have low to moderate levels of resistance to *H. armigera*. This has made it necessary to choose genotypes with a higher capacity to withstand or regenerate from pod damage [14]. This promising method of pest management is even environmentally beneficial due to screening under natural environmental conditions and ultimately host plant resistance was evaluated. The researchers may use this data to adopt efficient and environmentally friendly chickpea genotypes and management strategies for this pest.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Details of genotypes: Ten genotypes of chickpea with different growth habits were selected for their reaction to *H. armigera* under the screening studies. The source of these genotypes was obtained from Agriculture Research Station, Badnapur works under Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Agriculture University, Parbhani (MH) viz., JG-11, JG 62, ICC 92944, BDNG-797, KAK 2 (Kabuli), ICCL-86111(R), ICC 506, ICCV 3137 (S), BDNGK-798 (Kabuli) and ICCV 10. The experiment was conducted at the experimental farm of the Department of Agricultural Entomology, VNMKV, Parbhani during *Rabi* 2021-22 with three replications under randomized block design (RBD).

Source utilization:

The seeds were sown by dibbling during the 47th Meteorological week (25th Nov.). The standard dose of fertilizer was applied to all genotype tested for well growth. Other than that no other chemicals was sprayed. Three times hand weeding was done.

Method of observation:

Each replication plant of test genotype underwent weekly observations for the egg and larval populations of *H. armigera* from 50th MW to 7th MW (Meteorological weeks) of *rabi* 2021-22. The larvae of this insect pest rupture pods and penetrate into the pod and fed within, making seed unsuitable for human consumption [6]. To evaluate this effect of *H. armigera*, from pod initiation till plant harvest pod damage was monitored on every genotype. For estimation of pod damage per cent, from pod initiation until harvesting, injured and healthy pods from each plant were recorded and per cent pod damage calculated:

$$\text{Pod damage (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of damaged pods}}{\text{Total no. of pods}} \times 100$$

Accordingly, from vegetative to flowering and until pod formation stage of chickpea test genotypes, their mean number of eggs and larvae including the percentage of pod damage throughout the season presented here.

Yield correlation:

Significant positive correlation examined between detrimental association of grain production/plant *i.e.*, Yield and the number of eggs and larva [9]. Thus, correlation coefficient (r) was worked out between of *H. armigera* incidence with an average yield of chickpea. [12], [16], [20].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Screening evaluation of Ten chickpea genotypes in field for occurrence of eggs, larval population and pod damage per cent due to *H. armigera* under pesticide free condition was done during *rabi* season of 2021-22.

Eggs of pod borer (*H. armigera*) on chickpea genotypes throughout growing MW:

The information on population of eggs of pod borer, *H. armigera* on different chickpea genotypes under study all through 50th MW, 51th MW, 52th MW, 4th MW and 7th MW is presented in Table 1 and depicted in figure 1.

Table 1. Eggs population of *H. armigera* during 50th, 51th, 52th, 4th and 7th MW Met. Week on chickpea genotypes.

Genotypes	Number of Eggs of <i>H.armigera</i> /plant				
	50 th MW	51 th MW	52 th MW	4 th MW	7 th MW
JG-11	0.59 (0.95)	0.30 (1.01)	0.15 (0.72)	0.77 (1.30)	0.83 (1.34)
ICC 92944	0.63 (1.10)	0.34 (1.10)	0.19 (0.80)	0.63 (1.26)	0.70 (1.29)
KAK 2 (Kabuli)	0.85 (1.17)	0.47 (1.20)	0.13 (0.68)	0.37 (1.16)	0.43 (1.20)
ICC 506	0.60 (0.92)	0.20 (1.10)	0.12 (0.65)	0.11 (1.05)	0.18 (1.09)
BDNG-798 (Kabuli)	1.00 (1.25)	0.57 (1.27)	0.26 (0.90)	0.79 (1.32)	0.86 (1.35)
JG 62	0.76 (1.04)	0.32 (1.04)	0.19 (0.78)	0.53 (1.22)	0.60 (1.25)
BDNG-797	0.83 (1.13)	0.40 (1.13)	0.16 (0.75)	0.19 (1.08)	0.26 (1.12)
ICCL-86111	0.40 (0.86)	0.13 (0.92)	0.11 (0.57)	0.29 (1.13)	0.35 (1.16)
ICC 3137	1.10 (1.41)	0.70 (1.30)	0.27 (0.92)	1.23 (1.45)	1.30 (1.49)
ICCV 10	1.00 (1.25)	0.68 (1.29)	0.13 (0.67)	0.34 (1.15)	0.41 (1.18)
SE(±M)	0.07	0.06	0.059	0.08	0.07
CD @ 5%	0.22	0.18	0.173	0.24	0.21
CV %	10.55	8.86	9.361	10.12	9.86

Parenthesis figures of eggs population are $\sqrt{x+0.5}$

The data showed significant differences among the genotypes regarding egg population of *H. armigera*. The eggs population per plant appeared in different parallel ranges of 0.40 to 1.10 eggs/plant, 0.13 to 0.70 eggs/plant, 0.11 to 0.27 eggs/plant, 0.11 to 1.23 eggs/plant and 0.18 to 1.30 eggs/plant respectively during five MW. This result coincides with reference research

where 9 chickpea genotypes against *H. armigera* evaluated and the number of eggs of *H. armigera* on different genotypes varied from 2.30 to 15.74 eggs and lowest oviposition was recorded on Genotype 5282 [5]. ICCL 86111 performed well with the least number of eggs reported during 50th, 51th and 52th MW (0.40 eggs/plant, 0.13 eggs/plant and 0.11 eggs/plant respectively). After that during the 4th and 7th MW ICC 506 showed a least population of eggs viz., 0.11 eggs/plant and 0.18 eggs/plant respectively. ICC 3137 showed the highest level of eggs population appearance 11.10 eggs/plant, 0.70 eggs/plant, 0.27 eggs/plant, 1.23 eggs/plant and 1.30 eggs/plant during five weeks of observation respectively.

During 50th MW JG 11 (0.59 eggs/plant) followed after ICC 506 (0.60 eggs/plant) and JG 62 (0.76 eggs/plant) performed at par with ICCL 86111. During 51st MW ICC 506 (0.20 eggs/plant) followed by JG 11 (0.30 eggs/plant), JG 62 (0.32 eggs/plant) and ICC 92944 (0.34 eggs/plant) were found statistically significant and at par with well-performing genotypes. 52nd MW showed that ICC 506, KAK 2, ICCV 10 and JG 11 *i.e.*, 0.12, 0.13, 0.13 and 0.15 eggs/plant significantly at par with ICCL 86111. During the 4th MW BDNG 797 (0.19 eggs/plant) followed by ICCL 86111 (0.29 eggs/plant), ICCV 10 (0.34 eggs/plant) and KAK 2 (0.37 eggs/plant) performed well after ICCL 86111.

After evaluating 31 genotypes in the field for 100 days after germination showed the quantity of eggs/plants ranged highest in ICC 3137 (5.1 eggs/plants) among others [24]. This had also been discovered that the genotypes ICC-3137, K-850, and ICC-1403 were more defenseless and have privileged more eggs laying [23]. Ultimately during 7th MW BDNG 797 (0.26 eggs/plant) followed by ICCL 86111 (0.35 eggs/plant), ICCV 10 (0.41 eggs/plant), KAK 2 (0.43 eggs/plant) and JG 62 (0.60 eggs/plant) performed better for further recommendation.

3.2 Larval population of *H. armigera* on different chickpea genotypes throughout growing MW.

larval population of borer caterpillar, on different chickpea genotypes were undertook for study throughout plant growing ten weeks (50th, 51th, 52th, 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th and 7th MW) showed here (Table 2 and depicted in fig. 2).

The figures revealed significant differences among the genotypes regarding larval population of *H. armigera*. The number of larvae per plant of *H. armigera* during ten experimental MW appeared in different parallel ranges of 0.66 to 1.11 larvae / plant, 0.26 to 0.80 larvae / plant, 0.18 to 0.91 larvae / plant, 0.26 to 0.98 larvae / plant, 0.58 to 1.50 larvae / plant, 0.41 to 1.54 larvae per plant, 0.65 to 1.77 larvae / plant, 0.83 to 1.63 larvae / plant, 0.80 to 2.03 larvae / plant and 0.99 to 1.99 larvae / plant respectively on the chickpea genotypes under study. The result coincides with reference that BG-372, HC-1, SAKI-9516, Vijay and Avrodhi were relatively less susceptible as these harboured lower larval population (1.07 to 1.32 larvae/plant) [8].

The lowest number of larval populations during 50th, 51th, 52th, 2nd, 3rd, 6th MW recorded on genotypes ICCL 86111 (0.66 larvae/plant, 0.26 larvae/plant, 0.18 larvae/plant, 0.58 larvae/plant, 0.41 larvae/plant and 0.80 larvae/ plant respectively). ICC 506 during 4th, 5th and 7th MW showed 0.65 larvae/plant, 0.83 larvae/plant and 0.80 larvae/ plant respectively. But during 1st MW least larval population was reported on genotypes ICC 92944 (0.26 larvae/plant). Equivalent results were obtain according resistant genotype C 235 showed lowest larvae population (0.5/10 plants) and utmost number of larvae (3.0/10 plants) and susceptible genotype H 82-2 [11].

Table 2. Larval population of *H. armigera* on chickpea genotypes during growing meteorological weeks.

Genotype	No. of larval population of <i>H.armigera</i> /plant during MW									
	50 th MW	51 st MW	52 nd MW	1 st MW	2 nd MW	3 rd MW	4 th MW	5 th MW	6 th MW	7 th MW
JG-11	0.76 (1.01)	0.77 (1.32)	0.42 (1.15)	0.90 (1.23)	1.20 (1.59)	1.24 (1.63)	1.43 (1.55)	1.57 (1.59)	1.63 (1.68)	1.63 (1.70)
ICC 92944	0.88 (1.12)	0.38 (1.11)	0.44 (1.16)	0.26 (1.00)	0.84 (1.41)	0.88 (1.43)	0.96 (1.39)	1.10 (1.43)	1.16 (1.45)	1.17 (1.45)
KAK 2 (Kabuli)	0.92 (1.15)	0.49 (1.20)	0.61 (1.28)	0.70 (1.30)	0.87 (1.40)	0.91 (1.47)	0.90 (1.36)	1.03 (1.40)	1.10 (1.43)	1.11 (1.43)
ICC 506	0.86 (0.98)	0.31 (1.06)	0.38 (1.12)	0.57 (1.11)	0.64 (1.17)	0.68 (1.21)	0.65 (1.25)	0.83 (1.32)	1.00 (1.38)	0.99 (1.38)
BDNG-798 (Kabuli)	1.05 (1.29)	0.76 (1.30)	0.67 (1.32)	0.83 (1.23)	1.28 (1.63)	1.32 (1.67)	1.53 (1.59)	1.67 (1.63)	1.73 (1.65)	1.74 (1.65)
JG 62	0.89 (1.09)	0.50 (1.28)	0.56 (1.25)	0.77 (1.34)	0.95 (1.45)	0.99 (1.49)	1.07 (1.42)	1.20 (1.46)	1.30 (1.50)	1.31 (1.50)
BDNG-797	0.8 (1.19)	0.43 (1.15)	0.47 (1.18)	0.47 (1.13)	0.64 (1.17)	0.59 (1.21)	0.86 (1.33)	0.86 (1.33)	1.04 (1.40)	1.02 (1.38)
ICCL-86111	0.66 (0.92)	0.26 (0.98)	0.18 (0.93)	0.52 (1.10)	0.58 (1.10)	0.41 (1.10)	0.75 (1.31)	0.97 (1.38)	0.80 (1.33)	1.04 (1.39)
ICC 3137	1.11 (1.28)	0.80 (1.45)	0.91 (1.46)	0.98 (1.42)	1.50 (1.72)	1.54 (1.79)	1.77 (1.66)	1.63 (1.71)	2.03 (1.74)	1.99 (1.73)
ICCV 10	1.05 (1.20)	0.68 (1.27)	0.23 (0.98)	0.70 (1.27)	0.91 (1.41)	0.95 (1.49)	0.87 (1.35)	1.01 (1.39)	1.07 (1.42)	1.08 (1.42)
SE(±M)	0.06	0.04	0.08	0.15	0.13	0.17	0.06	0.076	0.05	0.07
CD @ 5%	0.18	0.12	0.26	0.45	0.39	0.38	0.18	0.227	0.15	0.22
CV %	10.44	9.92	8.864	10.62	10.15	10.19	9.80	8.947	8.69	8.57

Parenthesis figures of larval population are $\sqrt{x+0.5}$

As discussed earlier least number of larval populations was observed on ICCL 86111 but after that ICC 506 (0.86, 0.31, 0.38, 0.57, 0.64, 0.68, 0.65, 0.83, 1.00 and 0.99 larvae / plant) and BDNG 797 (0.8, 0.43, 0.47, 0.47, 0.64, 0.59, 0.86, 0.86, 1.04, 1.02 larvae / plant) during every screening week proved themselves better fit after ICCL 86111. Kabuli chickpea types viz., KAK 2 (0.92, 0.49, 0.61, 0.70, 0.87, 0.91, 0.90, 1.03, 1.10 and 1.11 larvae / plant) and BDNG 798 (1.05, 0.76, 0.67, 0.83, 1.28 1.32, 1.53, 1.67, 1.73 and 1.74 larvae / plant) also showed less than ICC 3137 but maximum positive response to larval population feeding preference than other genotypes during screening weeks. Other genotypes viz., JG-11, ICC 92944, JG 62 and ICCV 10 showed moderate level of resistance and medium level of infestation of larval population throughout MW.

Accordingly highest population of *H. armigera* larvae throughout experimental growing season in respective ten MW was recorded on ICC-3137 (1.11 larvae/plant, 0.80 larvae/plant, 0.91 larvae/plant, 0.98 larvae/plant, 1.50 larvae/plant, 1.54 larvae/plant, 1.77 larvae/plant, 1.63 larvae/plant, 2.03 larvae/plant and 1.99 larvae/plant respectively).

After assessing *H. armigera* resistance responses from 11 different chickpea cultivars Chaffe (14.32) and ICCV 10 also had the lowest larval populations whereas Phule G 5 (26.33), PG 8111 (24.90), GNG 465 (23.61) and BG 391 had the greatest larval incidence (23.31) [4].

Mean Pod damage, Eggs, Larval population and yield due to *H.armigera* during Met. Week on chickpea

The data pertaining mean eggs, larval population and pod damage per cent of gram pod borer, *H. armigera* on genotypes under study is presented in (Table 3 and depicted in fig. 3).

It is found that on genotypes indicated significant differences regarding eggs, larval population and pod damage due to *H. armigera*. The mean results were observed in the range of

0.24 to 1.06 eggs per plant, 0.51 to 1.46 larvae/plant and 3.36 to 9.85 per cent respectively on the different genotypes.

The lowest degree of mean eggs per plant, larvae per plant of *H. armigera* and pod damage per cent due to *H. armigera* was observed on genotype ICCL 86111 (0.24 eggs/plant, 0.51 larvae/plant and 3.36 per cent) which was at par with ICC 506 (0.27 eggs/plant, 0.64 larvae/plant and 3.93 per cent), BDNG 797 (0.35 eggs/plant, 0.67 larvae/plant and 4.26 per cent) and KAK 2 (0.43 eggs/plant, 0.80 larvae/plant and 7.25 per cent) respectively. Followed by ICCV 10 (0.49 eggs/plant and 0.83 larvae/plant), JG 11 (0.52 eggs/plant and 1.06 larvae/plant), ICC 92944 (0.52 eggs/plant and 0.82 larvae/plant). BDNG 798 (8.88 per cent) indicating moderate pod damage due to pod borer at par damage with after ICC 3137. Highest mean number of eggs per plant, larvae per plant of *H. armigera* and per cent pod damage due to *H. armigera* was observed on genotype (1.06 eggs/plant, 1.46 larvae /plant and 9.85 per cent).

Results are in accordance with reports that the pod damage varies from 9.43 to 24.80 per cent [15]. It is seen that variety Vijay had the least amount of pod damage (19.73 and 23.33%), followed by RSG 888 (20.46 and 27.67) but variety Samrat had the most pod damage (30.40 and 34.33%) [10]. Also genotypes ICC 506, ICCV 10, ICCL 86102, and ICCV 95992 were shown to have low pod damage ratings of 3 from one to nine scale [3]. Most promising strain, BRC-4, and the least vulnerable strain, BRC-1, both had pod damage levels of 9.38 and 21.49 per cent with grain yields of 0.333 and 0.137 kg/plot, respectively [19].

Table 3. Mean Eggs, Larval population, pod damage and yield due to *H.armigera* during Met. Week on chickpea

Genotype	Mean eggs-larval population and per cent pod damage			
	Eggs of <i>H.armigera</i> /plant	Larva of <i>H.armigera</i> /plant	Pod Damage (%)	Yield (Kg/Ha)
JG-11	0.52 (1.23)	1.06 (1.42)	7.72 (16.03)	1376
ICC 92944	0.52 (1.23)	0.82 (1.34)	5.46 (13.48)	1567
KAK 2 (Kabuli)	0.43 (1.19)	0.80 (1.33)	7.25 (15.55)	970
ICC 506	0.27 (1.12)	0.64 (1.28)	3.93 (11.43)	1654
BDNG-798 (Kabuli)	0.68(1.29)	1.18 (1.47)	8.88 (17.24)	1421
JG 62	0.47 (1.21)	0.88 (1.36)	7.15 (15.28)	1341
BDNG-797	0.35 (1.16)	0.67 (1.29)	4.26 (11.88)	1477
ICCL-86111	0.24 (1.11)	0.51 (1.22)	3.36 (10.50)	1705
ICC 3137	1.06 (1.42)	1.46 (1.56)	9.85 (18.21)	876
ICCV 10	0.49 (1.21)	0.83 (1.35)	5.88 (13.92)	1620
SE(±M)	0.03	0.03	0.56	19.40
CD @ 5%	0.08	0.10	1.61	58.10
CV %	8.46	8.89	9.82	17.80

Figures of eggs and larval population in parenthesis are $\sqrt{x+0.5}$

Figures of percentage in parenthesis are angular transformed values.

The figures on average grain yield of test chickpea genotypes is specified in Table 3 and fig 4. It ranged from 870 to 1705 kg/ha. The uppermost grain yield was recorded by genotypes ICCL 86111 (1705 kg/ha) which was at par with the genotypes ICC 506 (1654 kg/ha) followed by ICCV 10 (1620 kg/ha), ICC 92944 (1567 kg/ha), BDNG 797 (1477 kg/ha), BDNG 798 (1421 kg/ha), JG 11 (1376 kg/ha) and JG 62 (1341 kg/ha) respectively. The lowest grain yield among the genotypes tested were recorded by KAK 2 (970 kg / ha) and ICC 3137 (876 kg/ha).

It was found that the grain production per plot ranged from 23.33 to 192.00 gm /plant with a larval population ranging from 1 to 50 [18]. While comparing genotype ICC 506 to Annegeri, ICC 506 showed (2.08) and achieved a yield of 797 kg/ha, whereas Annigeri with higher damage rating (8.33) and achieved 620 kg/ha. Chaffa, the cultivar that experienced the least pod damage (9.55%), was the most resilient [13].

Correlation of yield with *H. armigera* damage parameters.

The chickpea yield showed significantly negative correlation (Table 4) with mean per cent pod damage ($r = -0.774$) and Mean Eggs of *H.armigera*, Mean Larval Population of

H.armigera ($r = -0.690, -0.688$, respectively) indicating correlation of higher pod damage with lower the yield of chickpea.

Table 4. Correlation (r) of yield with screening attributes against *H. armigera*

Sr. no	Screening attributes against <i>H. armigera</i>	Yield
1	Mean Eggs Population of <i>H.armigera</i>	-0.690
2	Mean Larval Population of <i>H.armigera</i>	-0.688
3	Mean Pod damage % due to <i>H.armigera</i>	-0.774**

**Significance Level at 0.01 % (0.765)

The present findings are supported by earlier research reports yield obtained in ICCV 10, ICC 506 and ICCL 86111 were 1641, 1887 and 2120 kg/ha., respectively [12]. Reference report describes that ICCV 10 exhibited high yield potential and ICCV 09118 also showed a grain yield potential of >15.2 q/ha. The genotypes ICCV 07104 and ICCV 10 showed a yield potential of >15.0 q/ha compared to 5 q/ha in ICC 3137 [2]. Decrease in grain yield was lowermost in resistant check [22].

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions could be drawn on the basis of present investigations.

- i. According present scenario and responses of different genotypes for eggs count, larval population and pod damage per cent, genotype *i.e.*, ICCL 86111, ICC 506, BDNG 797 and for Kabuli type KAK 2 were found promising with minimum mean pod damage and consistently showed tolerant reaction for entire season of crop.
- ii. Hence, The potential genotypes may be employed in a hybridization programme to develop high-yielding, pod borer-resistant, or tolerant chickpea varieties that might be used as one of the elements of integrated pest control.
- iii. Minor to Moderate level effect of *H. armigera* infestation on net yield can be expected.
- iv. Evaluating responses can support future pest management strategies.

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